

Tough Boys Start at Home? Investigating the Role of Home Environment on Conformity to Masculinity and Bystander Roles

Iqra Mubeen Bala¹ and Komala M.²

Human Development and Family Studies, Manasagangotri, Mysore, Karnataka¹
Department of Studies in Food Science & Nutrition, University of Mysore, Karnataka²

This study examined how Home Environment and Conformity to masculine norms influence pro-bullying bystander roles among middle school boys in India, a context where these relationships are under-examined. From a larger sample in an ongoing study, 281 male Bystanders (ages 10-13) in Mysore, India, were categorized into four Bystander roles (Assistants, Reinforcers, Defenders, Outsiders). The tools used included Home Environment Inventory (HEI) to assess family dynamics, while Indian Scale of Conformity to Masculinity (ISCM) measuring adherence to gender norms was used. Results indicated that stronger conformity to traditional masculine norms was significantly associated with a reduced likelihood of adopting pro-victim roles. Furthermore, pro-bully roles were significantly predicted by Home Environments characterized by higher levels of punishment and rejection. These results highlight that bystander role adoption is not solely a peer-driven phenomenon but is also rooted in family socialization and gender norms. This suggests a need for interventions that integrate school-based peer culture reforms with family-level strategies to foster prosocial behaviours while challenging rigid masculine norms that legitimize aggression.

Keywords: Adolescence, early- adolescents, middle school students, bystander roles, conformity to masculinity norms

Adolescence is a critical period of human development, marked by rapid biological, psychological, and social transitions. During this time, individuals start to form personal and social identities, gain more independence, and deal with new emotional and relationship challenges (Steinberg, 2014). They are particularly aware of peer approval and group dynamics which paves adolescence a chance for growth, but it also increases the risk of being exposed to forms of aggression and peer violence and other risky behaviours.

Within adolescence, the early period (ages 11-14) is particularly important, as the middle school years are characterized by heightened social sensitivity, identity exploration, and the desire to establish peer status (Thakkar et al., 2021; Watson, 2007). Consequently, the risk of bullying perpetration tends to peak during this developmental stage (Espelage & Holt, 2001). Defined as an intentional and repeated aggression, School Bullying involves a power imbalance between peers, and can take verbal, physical, relational, and digital forms (Olweus et al., 2004).

Although early research primarily focused on Bullies and

Victims, contemporary perspectives across globe have highlighted the role of peer Bystanders who witness bullying and whose responses can escalate or diminish its impact (Salmivalli et al., 1998; Hong & Espelage, 2012; Yun, 2020). Bystanders may adopt pro-bully roles (Assistants who help the bully or Reinforcers who encourage bullying through approval) or pro-victim roles (Defenders who intervene to support victims or Outsiders who withdraw from involvement). While Defenders can help reduce bullying, the majority of adolescents remain Outsiders, preferring to avoid involvement altogether (Kärnä et al., 2010; Yun, 2020). This underscores the importance of understanding the factors that influence bystander role adoption, particularly during early adolescence when identities and behavioural patterns are still being formed.

One such factor is gender socialization, especially the role of masculinity (Burns & Mahalik, 2008). Traditional masculine norms emphasize toughness, competitiveness, dominance, and emotional stoicism (Burtsev, 2023). For adolescent boys, conforming to these ideals often becomes a way to navigate peer expectations and secure social status (Leone et al., 2016; Koon, 2013). Within this framework, supporting or encouraging bullying can be seen as a performance of masculinity- a way to demonstrate strength, avoid appearing weak, and align with dominant peer norms. Conversely, defending victims may be perceived as risky, inviting retaliation or peer rejection (Espelage et al., 2012; Bala et al., 2022). Theoretically, this aligns with gender role conflict theory, which argues that strict adherence to masculine norms restricts emotional expression, reduces empathy, and fosters aggression (Good & Wood, 1995; Hammer & Vogel, 2010).

While much research on masculinity has focused on adult men or older adolescents, little is known about how these norms are first absorbed in early adolescence and how they shape behaviours like

Author Note

¹Iqra Mubeen Bala, Senior Research Scholar, Human Development and Family Studies, Manasagangotri, Mysore, Karnataka
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0047-4156

²Dr. Komala M., Professor, Human Development and Family Studies Department of Studies in Food Science & Nutrition, University of Mysore, Karnataka
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4540-807X**

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Iqra Mubeen Bala, Senior Research Scholar, Human Development and Family Studies, Manasagangotri, Mysore, Karnataka
E-mail: iqramubeen@foodsci.uni-mysore.ac.in

bystander role adoption. This is a critical gap because patterns of aggression, conformity, and emotional suppression are often established during this stage in everyday interactions at home and school (Ingram et al., 2019).

The Home Environment is central to this process. Families act as primary agents of socialization, shaping beliefs about gender, power, and emotion from an early age. Positive environments characterized by warmth, nurturance, and consistent reinforcement promote empathy, emotional expression, and defending behaviours (Thornberg et al., 2017; Zhong et al., 2024). In contrast, negative environments marked by punitive discipline, inconsistency, or rejection are associated with pro-bully roles, reinforcing aggression and emotional suppression (Baldry & Farrington, 2005; Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2016). Moreover, family violence and authoritarian parenting can undermine the benefits of otherwise supportive practices, reduce empathy and weakening prosocial bystander behaviour (Zhong et al., 2024).

In the Indian cultural context, this dynamic takes on particular importance. Traditional gender roles remain deeply embedded across both rural and urban contexts, with masculinity often framed as strength, authority, and emotional endurance. Boys frequently receive direct and indirect messages that discourage vulnerability and valorize dominance, both within the family and in peer settings (Seidler et al., 2016; Burtsev, 2023). Yet, empirical work on bystander roles in India remains limited, with only a handful of studies beginning to examine how cultural norms and family dynamics interact to shape adolescents' responses in bullying situations (Bala et al., 2022).

The present study seeks to address this gap by examining the links between home environment, conformity to masculinity, and bystander role adoption among middle school boys. Specifically, we investigate whether negative or rigid home Environments foster stricter conformity to masculine norms and greater likelihood of pro-bully roles (Assistants, Reinforcers), whereas positive environments characterized by nurturance and reward encourage pro-victim roles (Defenders, Outsiders). By situating these questions within the Indian context, this study may contribute to a deeper understanding of how early family socialization and gender norms jointly shape school bullying dynamics.

Ultimately, this research highlights that bullying cannot be understood solely as an individual or peer-level phenomenon. Instead, it reflects broader processes of gender and emotional socialization rooted in the family. Addressing these dynamics requires interventions that work at both the school and family level, fostering parental warmth and emotional openness while challenging rigid masculine norms that legitimize aggression.

Research Question

Do male adolescents who are raised in negative or rigid Home Environments tend to internalize stricter masculine norms, and are these adolescents more likely to take on pro-bullying bystander roles in school bullying?

By focusing on this targeted relationship, the study aims to contribute new insights into how domestic socialization shapes peer group dynamics and bullying culture through the lens of gender norm internalization in Indian context. In doing so, the study contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of how early socialization, gender identity, and peer dynamics interact to shape

male bystander behaviour. It underscores the importance of looking beyond the immediate school context and instead considering how family structures and emotional environments contribute to the reinforcement of harmful social norms. It calls for early intervention, not only in school anti-bullying programs but also in parenting practices and gender-sensitive education that tackle toxic masculinity at its roots.

Method

Participants

The study was conducted on male students studying in private, English-medium schools located within Mysore City, Karnataka, India. The city is administratively divided into North and South education blocks, and schools from both zones were represented in the sample.

The final sample for this analysis consisted of 281 male students, aged 10-13 years, from Grades 5 to 7. All participants in this final sample were identified as having adopted various Bystander roles in school bullying incidents using Participant Role Questionnaire (Salmivalli & Voeten, 2004). This targeted subsample was drawn from a larger initial cohort of 939 students. Within that larger group, a total of 808 students were classified as Bystanders, distributed across four distinct roles: Assistants ($n = 127$), Reinforcers ($n = 132$), Defenders ($n = 171$), and Outsiders ($n = 378$).

Sampling Design and Procedure

A multistage stratified sampling method was employed to recruit a representative sample. The process involved several distinct stages.

First, nine private schools were selected from the North and South education blocks of Mysore based on criteria including student enrolment size, administrative permission, and accessibility. To ensure participant confidentiality and encourage honest responses, student names were first obtained from a designated school teacher. Each student was then assigned a unique identification number. This number, rather than the student's name, was used on all questionnaires and remained consistent throughout the study.

After securing ethical clearance and approval from the Block Education Officers, a total of 1,236 questionnaires were distributed to eligible students. The sample was refined through the following steps:

School Withdrawal: One all boys- school withdrew participation due to parental concerns, resulting in the exclusion of 247 students.

Data Screening: An additional 50 participants were excluded due to incomplete questionnaires ($n = 15$), lack of consent ($n = 5$), parental withdrawal of consent ($n = 12$), or student absence during data collection ($n = 16$). This yielded a final sample of 939 students.

Role Classification: Using the Participant Role Questionnaire (Salmivalli & Voeten, 2004) these 939 students were categorized based on their involvement in bullying. A total of, 808 were identified as Bystanders, distributed across four roles: Assistants ($n = 127$), Reinforcers ($n = 132$), Defenders ($n = 171$), and Outsiders ($n = 378$).

Subsample Extraction: For the present analysis, the sample was further limited to the 281 male students from 808 identified bystanders to allow for a focused investigation of conformity to masculine norms.

This structured sampling process allowed for targeted analysis of gender-specific predictors of Bystander roles.

Research Design

A quantitative, exploratory research design was employed to examine the relationship between Home Environment, Conformity to Masculinity, and various Bystander Roles among early adolescent boys in middle schools. The design focused on identifying how socio-emotional climate at home contributes to the internalization of masculine role norms, and how this internalization predicts boys' roles as Pro-Bullies (i.e., Assistants & Reinforcers) or Pro-Victims (Defenders & Outsiders) bullying incidents.

Measures

Socio-demographic Questionnaire. A self-developed questionnaire collected data on student demographics (age, grade), family structure (nuclear or joint), and parental information (age, education, occupation, family income).

Participant Role Questionnaire (PRQ), developed by (Salmivalli & Voeten, 2004) a validated measure for categorizing student roles in bullying situations. To ensure a shared understanding and establish a clear timeframe, the questionnaire first provided students with the following definitions for behaviour occurring within the past academic year:

Bullying: An intentional & repeated behaviour that hurts, harms, or humiliates a student, either physically or emotionally. This can happen offline or online on social platforms by another child or someone you know at school.

This School: Activities happening in school buildings, on school grounds, on school buses, and at places that hold school-sponsored events or activities.

The 15 items assess behaviour corresponding to five primary roles:

Bully, Assistant (e.g., helping the bully), Reinforcer (e.g., encouraging the bully), Defender (e.g., supporting the victim), and Outsider (e.g., staying away from the situation). An additional three items assessing the Victim role were adapted from the work of Kärnä et al. (2010) a subscale which has demonstrated strong internal consistency in previous research (e.g., Cronbach's $\alpha = .85$). Participants rated how frequently their peers engaged in each behaviour on a 3-point scale, where 0 = never, 1 = sometimes, and 2 = often. For each role, a score was calculated by averaging the ratings of the corresponding items, resulting in a continuous score ranging from 0.00 to 2.00 for each participant on each role scale. Participants were then assigned to the Bystander role for which they received the highest score in among the four Roles.

For the logistic regression analysis, these four bystander roles were further categorized into two broader groups. The Assistant and Reinforcer roles were combined to form a pro-bully group, while the Defender and Outsider roles were combined to form a pro-victim group. This classification allowed for a direct analysis of how conformity to masculine norms and Home Environment characteristics predicted bystander alignment.

Home Environment Inventory (HEI). The 34-item short form of the HEI (Datta & Dutta, 2018) was used to assess the quality of participants' Home Environments across seven domains: Protectiveness, Nurturance, Social Isolation, Reward, Deprivation of Privileges, Nurturance, and Rejection. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (0 = *Never* to 4 = *Mostly*). For analysis, these were categorized into a Positive Home Environment composite (Protectiveness, Reward, Nurturance) and a Negative Home Environment composite (Punishment, Social Isolation, Deprivation of Privileges, Rejection). The domains were further categorized to

capture positive vs. negative aspects of Home Environment:

Positive Home Environment: Total scores from Protectiveness, Reward, and Nurturance

Negative Home Environment: Total scores from Punishment, Social Isolation, Deprivation of Privileges, and Rejection

Higher scores in Positive Home Environment reflect a nurturing, supportive, and protective family climate, while higher scores in Negative Home Environment indicate greater exposure to punitive, rejecting, or isolating practices.

Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 ("*Never*") to 4 ("*Mostly*"), with higher scores indicating stronger presence of each domain in the participant's home life. The scale has demonstrated strong reliability and validity for Indian adolescent populations (Datta & Datta, 2018).

Indian Scale of Conformity to Masculinity (ISCM): Conformity to traditional masculine norms was measured using the Indian Scale of Conformity to Masculinity (ISCM), an 8-item self-report instrument developed specifically for this study. The development of a new measure was necessary as widely used Western instruments, such as the Conformity to Masculine Norms Inventory (CMNI; Mahalik et al., 2003) contain subscales and items (e.g., the "Playboy" subscale) that are not culturally or developmentally appropriate for middle school students in India.

The ISCM was designed to be culturally grounded, assessing beliefs across three core domains: (a) dominance in family roles, (b) physical strength and aggression, and (c) emotional expression and help-seeking. For each item, participants select one of three response options reflecting a Traditional Masculine View (e.g., 'Only men'), a Gender-Neutral View (e.g., 'Both Men & Women'), or a Reverse-Traditional View (e.g., 'Only women'). Responses are scored on a 3-point scale (1 = least traditional, 3 = most traditional), with five items reverse-scored to ensure that a higher total score consistently reflects greater conformity to traditional masculine norms. Total scores can range from 8 to 24 and were treated as a continuous variable. A full description of the scale's development, validation, and psychometric properties is provided in the Results section.

Ethical Clearance

The study obtained ethical clearance from the University of Mysore Ethical Committee, ensuring adherence to the ethical guidelines for research involving human participants.

Pilot Study

Before the main data collection, a pilot study was conducted with 45 middle school students in 5th to 7th grades. These students came from schools with similar demographic characteristics to those in the main study. The goal was to evaluate how clear, understandable, and appropriate the Indian Scale of Conformity to Masculinity (ISCM) is for this age group. Feedback from the pilot participants confirmed that the tool is practical and showed that it is valid for use with adolescents in the selected age range.

Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from school authorities and parents. Oral consent was also secured from the participating students. Participants were assured that their involvement was voluntary and anonymous. They were informed of their right to withdraw at any time and that their responses would remain confidential. No monetary benefit was given to participants.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS 20.0 and JASP 19.05. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the sample characteristics. A one-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post-hoc tests was used to examine differences in Home Environment across the four bystander roles. Pearson correlations were calculated to assess the relationships between Home Environment and conformity to masculinity. Finally, a binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether Home Environment and conformity to masculinity predicted membership in the pro-bully versus pro-victim bystander groups. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$. In addition to the primary analyses, the 3D surface plot of the regression results was generated using Python with the Matplotlib and Scipy libraries.

Results

Scale Development and Psychometrics of the ICSM

The ICSM was developed as a culturally specific measure of conformity to masculine norms in middle school students. An initial pool of 12 items was reviewed for content validity by a panel of four senior academics in the field of Human Development and Family Studies. Based on their quantitative ratings and qualitative feedback, 4 items were eliminated, resulting in the final 8-item scale. The content validity of the final scale was excellent, with an overall Scale-Content Validity Index (S-CVI/Ave) of .91 (see Table 1). A pilot study with 45 middle school students further confirmed the instrument's face validity and age-appropriateness.

Table 1
Expert Content Validity Rating on Items of ICSM- Scale

Item No.	Item Statement	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	I-CVI	Aiken's V
1	Who should be the primary breadwinner?	4	4	4	4	1.00	1.00
2	Who should have the final say in important family decisions?	4	3	4	3	1.00	0.83
3	Who should be a homemaker?	4	4	4	4	1.00	1.00
4	Who should assume the role of leadership dynamics within the household?	4	4	3	3	1.00	0.83
5	Who should show more aggression and assertiveness?	4	4	3	4	1.00	0.92
6	From whom should emotional support be sought?	4	4	4	4	1.00	1.00
7	Who should have stronger and bigger body stature?	3	2	3	2	0.50	0.42
8	Who should ask for help from others?	4	2	4	4	0.75	0.75

Note. I-CVI = Item-Content Validity Index. Aiken's V is a coefficient of content validity. Item 7 was retained for theoretical importance and reworded based on expert feedback to reflect social expectations rather than biology. So, it was reworded from "Who should have stronger and bigger body stature?" to "Who is expected to be physically stronger and bigger in body build?"

Table 1
Reliability Statistics for the Indian Scale of Conformity to Masculinity

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Coefficient ?	0.780	0.020	0.742	0.819

The internal consistency of the 8-item ICSM in the current sample was acceptable (Cronbach's $\alpha = .78$) (Table 2). An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) supported the scale's construct validity. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure was .83 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant, $\chi^2(28) = 644.89, p < .001$, indicating the data were suitable for factor analysis. The EFA revealed a single, robust factor that explained 36.7% of the total variance, with all 8 items demonstrating strong factor loadings (see Table 3).

Table 3
Exploratory Factor Analysis and Psychometric Properties of the ICSM Scale

A. Item Loadings and MSA	Factor 1	Uniqueness	MSA
ICSM_1	0.575	0.669	0.828
ICSM_2	0.680	0.538	0.620
ICSM_3	0.711	0.495	0.837
ICSM_4	0.665	0.558	0.818

ICSM_5	0.712	0.493	0.886
ICSM_6	0.761	0.420	0.821
ICSM_7	0.569	0.677	0.907
ICSM_8	0.436	0.810	0.811
B. Factor Characteristics		<i>Value</i>	
Eigenvalue (Factor 1)	2.94		
Proportion of Variance	0.367		
Cumulative Variance	0.367		

Note. Results from a single-factor solution using Principal Component Analysis. MSA = Measure of Sampling Adequacy; KMO = Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin

Preliminary Analyses

Table 4
Preliminary Tests for Assumption of Normality of Variables in Study

	Total Score Masculinity Conformity to	Total Score Positive Home Environment	Total Score Negative Home Environment
Mean (M)	17.07	29.26	37.43
Std. Deviation (SD)	3.817	8.218	6.446
Skewness	-0.505	0.413	0.016
Kurtosis	-0.500	-0.499	-0.003
Shapiro-Wilk	0.954	0.974	0.995
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.520
Total Number of Sample (N)	281		

Table 4 depicts the results of Assumption of Normality for the variables in the study, these checks indicated that while some variables deviated from perfect normality (Shapiro-Wilk $p < 0.05$ for certain subscales), skewness and kurtosis values remained within acceptable thresholds (± 2 ; George & Mallery, 2010; Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012; Kim, 2013). Visual inspection of the histograms and Q-Q plots (see Figures 2-4) also suggested that the deviations were not severe. Given that ANOVA and regression are robust to minor violations of normality with larger sample sizes (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013; Kim, 2013) the analyses were conducted without data transformation.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 5

Distribution of Personal and Family Variables of Sample

Variable	Code	Frequency n	Valid Percent (%)
Age	≤11 yrs	84	30.0
	≤12 yrs	197	70.0
Class	5th class	94	34.0
	6th class	72	26.0
	7th class	115	40.0
Birth Order	First Born	109	39.0
	Later Borns	172	61.0
Religion	Hindus	152	54.0
	Other	129	46.0
Fathers' Age	<45 yrs	157	56.0
	45yrs and above	124	44.0
Mothers' Age	>35 yrs	72	26.0
	35yrs and above	209	74.0
Fathers' Education	PU and Below	137	49.0
Mothers' Education	Degree & Above	144	51.0
Fathers' Occupation	PU and Below	159	57.0
Mothers' Occupation	Degree & Above	122	43.0
Family Type	Business	129	46.0
Total family Income	Salaried	152	54.0
	Homemaker	191	68.0
Total Sample	Working	90	32.0
	Nuclear Family	225	80.0
Total family Income	Others	56	20.0
	20000 and below	125	80.0
Total family Income	Above 20000	156	20.0
	Total Sample	281	

Note. Distribution of Bystander Roles in Sample

The distribution of bystander roles revealed that the majority of participants were Outsiders (50%), followed by Reinforcers (20%), Defenders (16%), and Assistants (14%). Demographic characteristics of the 281 participants are presented in Table 5. The sample was predominantly Hindu (54%), from nuclear families (80%), and had a total family income of ₹20,000 or below (80%).

Home Environment and Bystander Roles

Table 6

One-Way ANOVA Results for Home Environment Subscales across Bystander Roles

Subscale	F	p
Reward	29.04	<0.001

Punishment	19.26	<0.001
Nurturance	41.08	<0.001
Protectiveness	38.96	<0.001
Social Isolation	2.41	0.067
Deprivation of Privileges	4.05	0.008
Rejection	6.90	<0.001

A one-way ANOVA was conducted (Table 6) to examine differences in Home Environment subscales across Bystander roles (Assistants, Reinforcers, Defenders, Outsiders). As indicated by results, significant effects were observed for Reward ($F = 29.04, p < 0.001$), Punishment ($F = 19.26, p < 0.001$), Nurturance ($F = 41.08, p < 0.001$), and Protectiveness ($F = 38.96, p < 0.001$). Smaller but significant effects emerged for Deprivation of Privileges ($F = 4.05, p = .008$) and Rejection ($F = 6.90, p < 0.001$). Social Isolation showed no significant group differences ($F = 2.41, p = 0.067$).

Table 7

Significant Pairwise Comparisons (Tukey HSD) of Bystander Roles on Home Environment Subscales

Subscale	Group 1	Group 2	Mean Diff	p
Reward	Assistants	Reinforcers	-2.2	0.0153
	Assistants	Defenders	4.03	0.001
Reward	Reinforcers	Defenders	6.23	0.001
	Defenders	Outsiders	-5.09	0.001
Punishment	Assistants	Defenders	-2.79	0.001
	Assistants	Outsiders	-2.21	0.001
Punishment	Reinforcers	Defenders	-2.95	0.001
	Reinforcers	Outsiders	-2.37	0.001
Nurturance	Assistants	Defenders	4.46	0.001
	Reinforcers	Defenders	5.14	0.001
Nurturance	Defenders	Outsiders	-5.42	0.001
	Assistants	Defenders	4.25	0.001
Protectiveness	Reinforcers	Defenders	5.12	0.001
	Defenders	Outsiders	-4.88	0.001
Social Isolation	Reinforcers	Outsiders	1.35	0.0431
	Reinforcers	Defenders	-2.11	0.0093
Deprivation of privileges	Defenders	Outsiders	1.8	0.01
	Assistants	Defenders	-2.07	0.0067
Rejection	Reinforcers	Defenders	-2.56	0.0001
	Defenders	Outsiders	1.48	0.019

A Tukey HSD post-hoc analysis (Table 7) was conducted to examine pairwise differences between the four bystander roles (Assistants, Reinforcers, Defenders, Outsiders) across the Home Environment subscales. All significant comparisons are detailed in Table 7.

On the Reward subscale, Defenders reported significantly higher scores than Assistants (Mean Difference = 4.03, $p < 0.001$) and Reinforcers (Mean Difference = 6.23, $p < 0.001$). Outsiders, in turn, scored significantly lower than Defenders (Mean Difference = -5.09, $p < 0.001$). A significant difference was also found between Assistants and Reinforcers (Mean Difference = -2.20, $p = 0.015$).

For the positive parenting domains of Nurturance and Protectiveness, a consistent pattern emerged. Defenders scored significantly higher on Nurturance than both Assistants (Mean Difference = 4.46, $p < 0.001$) and Reinforcers (Mean Difference =

5.14, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, Defenders scored higher on protectiveness than Assistants (Mean Difference = 4.25, $p < 0.001$) and Reinforcers (Mean Difference = 5.12, $p < 0.001$). On both subscales, Outsiders scored significantly lower than Defenders.

Figure 2

Frequency Distribution of Scores and Q-Q Plots for Total Conformity to Masculinity

Figure 3

Frequency Distribution of Scores and Q-Q Plots for Total Positive Home Environment

Figure 4

Frequency Distribution of Scores and Q-Q Plots for Total Positive Home Environment

Regarding negative parenting domains, pro-bully roles reported higher scores on Punishment. Both Assistants and Reinforcers scored significantly higher than Defenders ($p < .001$) and Outsiders ($p < .001$). For Rejection, Assistants (Mean Difference = -2.07 , $p = 0.007$) and Reinforcers (Mean Difference = -2.56 , $p < .001$) scored significantly higher than Defenders.

On the Deprivation of Privileges subscale, Defenders scored significantly higher than Reinforcers (Mean Difference = -2.11 , $p = 0.009$) and Outsiders (Mean Difference = 1.80 , $p = 0.010$). Finally, on Social Isolation, Reinforcers scored significantly higher than Outsiders (Mean Difference = 1.35 , $p = 0.043$).

Correlations and Regression Analysis

Table 8

Pearson Correlations between Conformity to Masculinity and Home Environment Subscales

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Conformity to Masculinity	-	-.20**	.14*	-.24**	-.23**	-.14*	.13*	.05
2. Reward		-	-.13*	.35**	.37**	.02	-.07	-.12
3. Punishment			-	-.10	-.10	-.03	.02	.13*
4. Nurturance				-	.44**	-.04	-.17**	-.14*
5. Protectiveness					-	.02	-.10	-.06
6. Social Isolation						-	.09	.09
7. Deprivation of Privileges							-	-.02
8. Rejection								-

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

The correlation analysis (Table 8) revealed meaningful associations between conformity to masculinity and adolescents' perceptions of their Home Environment. Conformity to masculinity was negatively correlated with Reward ($r = .20$, $p < 0.01$), Nurturance ($r = .24$, $p < 0.01$), and Protectiveness ($r = .23$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that boys with stronger adherence to traditional masculine norms perceive their homes as less supportive, nurturing, and protective. Conversely, conformity to masculinity was positively correlated with Punishment ($r = .14$, $p < 0.05$) and Deprivation of Privileges (r

$= .13$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that stricter or punitive environments may reinforce conformity to masculine role expectations. Associations with Social Isolation ($r = .14$, $p < 0.05$) and Rejection ($r = .05$, ns) were weaker, though generally aligned with the broader pattern. Together, these findings support the notion that the internalization of masculinity norms among boys is closely linked to the emotional climate of their Home Environment, with supportive homes discouraging rigid conformity and punitive contexts reinforcing it.

Table 9

Logistic Regression Predicting Bystander Group (Pro-bullies vs. Pro-victims) from Conformity to Masculinity and Home Environment Subscales

Predictor	B (SE)	OR [Exp(B)]	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Intercept	5.20 (1.33)	-	2.60	7.79	<0.001
Conformity (Moderate vs Low)	-1.57 (0.47)	0.21	-2.48	-0.65	<0.001
Conformity (High vs. Low)	-1.75 (0.54)	0.17	-2.80	-0.70	0.001
Reward	0.04 (0.04)	1.04	-0.04	0.12	0.291
Punishment	-0.36 (0.06)	0.70	-0.48	-0.23	<0.001
Nurturance	-0.03 (0.05)	0.97	-0.13	0.08	0.630
Protectiveness	0.04 (0.05)	1.04	-0.07	0.14	0.507
Social Isolation	0.10 (0.05)	1.11	0.01	0.19	0.031
Deprivation of Privileges	-0.04 (0.05)	0.96	-0.13	0.04	0.323
Rejection	-0.14(0.05)	0.87	-0.25	-0.04	0.005

Note. The dependent variable was coded as 1 = Pro-victim, 0 = Pro-bully. The reference group for Conformity to Masculinity is the "Low" conformity group. OR = Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; B = unstandardized coefficient; SE = standard error. The overall model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(9) = 86.36$, $p < .001$. Nagelkerke $R^2 = .238$.

A binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether conformity to masculinity and dimensions of the Home Environment predicted membership in pro-bully versus pro-victim bystander roles (Table 9). The overall model was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) with a Pseudo R^2 of .238, indicating that the predictors explained a meaningful proportion of variance in role classification.

Results showed that boys with moderate ($OR = 0.21, p < 0.001$) or high ($OR = 0.17, p = 0.001$) conformity to masculinity were significantly less likely to be in pro-victim roles compared to boys with low conformity. Among Home Environment dimensions, higher punishment ($OR = 0.70, p < 0.001$) and higher rejection ($OR = 0.87, p = 0.005$) decreased the likelihood of being in pro-victim roles, whereas greater social isolation slightly increased the likelihood ($OR = 1.11, p = 0.031$). Other subscales (Reward, Nurturance, Protectiveness, & Deprivation of privileges) showed differences but were not significant predictors.

Together, these findings suggest that both masculinity norms and negative Home Environment characteristics (especially punishment & rejection) play an important role in shaping whether adolescents align with pro-bully or pro-victim bystander. This predictive relationship between Higher conformity to masculinity and a more punitive Home Environment is visualized in the 3D model (Fig. 5), which illustrates that the probability of being a pro-bully is highest when both risk factors are present.

Figure 5

Predicted Probability of Adopting a Pro-Bully Bystander Role

Note. The 3D surface plot illustrates the predicted probability of adopting a pro-bully bystander role as a function of both conformity to masculinity and punishment score. Higher points on the surface indicate a greater probability.

Discussion

This study provides critical evidence that bystander behaviour among adolescent boys is not simply a peer-group phenomenon but is profoundly shaped by the interplay of family environment and internalized masculine norms. This core finding is evident even in the initial distribution of bystander roles.

The majority of participants (50%) were classified as Outsiders, aligning with a substantial body of research indicating that passive avoidance is a common response in peer bullying situations (Kärnä et al., 2010; Salmivalli et al., 1996; Yun, 2020). This passivity is often driven by a diffusion of responsibility or a fear of negative

social consequences (Latané & Darley, 1970). While Indian research on bystander roles is still developing, the findings from this study match initial reports from the region (Bala et al., 2022). The relatively small percentage of defenders, at 16%, highlights the social risks, such as retaliation or exclusion, that affects adolescents decisions to intervene (Thornberg, 2015). This shows a clear need for culturally relevant programs that not only teach defending skills but also aim to lower the social costs of helping within peer groups. The correlation analysis showed an important connection between boys' conformity to masculine norms and their views on the home environment. Specifically, conformity to masculinity was linked to less supportive aspects like reward, nurturance, and protectiveness, and more related to punitive aspects like punishment and loss of privileges. This indicates that boys who strictly follow traditional masculine ideals often come from homes they view as less supportive and more controlling (Zhong et al., 2024a). This finding resonates with theories of gender socialization, which posit that harsh or rejecting parenting styles can enforce restrictive gender roles and legitimize aggression as a valid masculine trait (Baldry & Farrington, 2005; Burtsev, 2023; Leaper & Friedman, 2007). The addition of Gender Schema Theory (Bem, 1981) helps explain the cognitive mechanism at play: boys may develop a mental framework, or 'schema,' for masculinity based on what their family environment models and reinforces, strengthening the belief that aggression is a core part of being 'male.' Conversely, a warm and supportive home climate appears to buffer against rigid masculinity by fostering empathy, emotional regulation, and prosocial values (Nickerson et al., 2008; Thornberg et al., 2017).

The ANOVA results further illuminated the influence of Home Environment on specific bystander roles. Pro-victim roles (defenders & outsiders) were linked to homes perceived as higher in reward, nurturance, and protectiveness. In contrast, pro-bully roles (assistants & reinforcers) were associated with greater exposure to punishment and rejection. This pattern strongly supports the idea that parenting practices are a key antecedent to how adolescents behave in bullying incidents (Saleh et al., 2021; Zhong et al., 2024b). These findings are consistent with Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) which suggests that aggressive or passive behaviours are learned through observation and reinforcement within the family. Prior research confirms that positive parenting is a strong predictor of defending behaviour (Polanin et al., 2012; Pronk et al., 2015; Thornberg et al., 2017) whereas punitive and rejecting environments increase the likelihood of aligning with aggressors (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2016; Jenkins & Nickerson, 2017; Zhong et al., 2024; Moon & Oh, 2018).

Post-hoc analyses provided a more granular view of these dynamics. Defenders consistently reported the most supportive Home Environments, reinforcing the conclusion that nurturing parenting directly fosters the courage and empathy required to defend others (Zhong et al., 2024a). Conversely, the high levels of punishment and rejection reported by Assistants and Reinforcers highlight how harsh parenting can model aggressive and anti-social solutions to conflict. Interestingly, outsiders reported a Home Environment less supportive than defenders, suggesting that their passive disengagement may stem from a lack of positive reinforcement for prosocial behaviour. This passivity can be understood through the lens of moral disengagement, where individuals rationalize their inaction, a process that may be more common in environments where prosociality is not actively encouraged (Gini et al., 2015).

The logistic regression analysis solidified the dual influence of masculinity and parenting on bystander roles. High conformity to masculine norms and exposure to a punitive and rejecting Home Environment emerged as a significant risk profile for adopting pro-bully roles. This powerful combination suggests that when boys are socialized to be "tough" at home through harsh discipline, they are more likely to endorse norms of dominance and aggression in their peer groups, making them less likely to intervene on behalf of a victim (Poteat et al., 2009).

Theoretically, the results are highly in agreement with Gender Role Conflict Theory, where strict adherence to traditional masculine norms, such as suppression of emotions and a need for dominance, can lead to psychological distress and maladaptive actions like aggression (Good & Wood, 1995; Hammer & Vogel, 2010; O'Neil, 2015; Addis & Mahalik, 2003; Berke et al., 2021; Woodbrown, 2018). Cultural standards that establish masculinity can prevent empathic reactions and reinforce dominance, causing boys to view the action of defending a victim as incompatible with their defined gender roles (Burtsev, 2023; Topçu & Baker, 2012). This is particularly significant within the Indian cultural context, where deeply ingrained aspects of masculinity and hierarchical family structures most often overlap to shape adolescent behaviours (Srivastava, 2015).

These results can also be explained by Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1969). A secure attachment, based on parental warmth and protectiveness, can give youths a 'secure base' that they feel safe enough to take social risks, like standing up for a victim. Conversely, an insecure attachment, potentially stemming from a rejecting or punitive environment, could lead to either anxious avoidance (the Outsider role) or externalizing behaviours (the Pro-bully roles) as maladaptive coping strategies (Zhong et al., 2024b).

Thus, the current study demonstrates that bystander behaviour is not merely a peer-driven phenomenon but is deeply rooted in family socialization and gender norm conformity. The findings underscore the necessity of a social-ecological approach to bullying prevention that moves beyond the schoolyard (Swearer & Hymel, 2015). Effective interventions in India must adopt a two-pronged strategy: addressing peer culture within schools while simultaneously engaging families. Programs aimed at promoting parental warmth and reducing punitive discipline, coupled with school-based initiatives that challenge restrictive masculine norms, hold the greatest promise for fostering a generation of boys who are more likely to act as prosocial defenders (Banyard, 2024).

Limitations and Future Directions

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. The cross-sectional design prevents the inference of causality; for instance, it is possible that boys' aggressive behaviours elicit more punitive parenting, rather than the other way around. Furthermore, the reliance on self-report data may be subject to social desirability bias. The findings are also specific to middle school boys from private schools in Mysore City, and further research is needed to determine their generalizability to other populations, including girls, students in public schools, and adolescents in diverse geographical locations across other Indian states. Future research should employ longitudinal designs to untangle causal pathways and incorporate observational methods.

Conclusion

This study underscores how, even in early adolescence, boys begin

to internalize masculine norms that meaningfully shape their roles as Bystanders in bullying situations. Although still in middle school, participants demonstrated behavioural patterns closely linked to the emotional climate and disciplinary structure of their Home Environments. The findings suggest that family dynamics during this formative stage may not only influence immediate peer interactions but also contribute to the early consolidation of rigid gender norms. By focusing on this younger cohort, the study draws attention to a critical developmental window where targeted interventions can promote empathy, reduce conformity to harmful masculine ideals, and encourage prosocial responses to bullying.

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